

Gastronomy of Pesan Tlengis as a Tourism Attraction in Werdi Bhuwana Village Bali

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ABSTRACT: The general purpose of this research is to improve and develop Indonesia's tourism development, especially rural tourism attraction in Bali, through developing traditional Balinese food so that it is known globally Abroad. However, the development of traditional food has not been achieved as expected. This happens because local food has not been explored in rural areas which are very abundant with culinary potential from nature to the fullest. One example is the food product pesan tlengis which is processed into delicious dishes and comes from the dregs of the process of making virgin coconut oil in Werdi Bhuwana Village. This study discusses in depth the forms of gastronomy that can be developed into a tourist attraction, and the efforts that can be made from the gastronomic meaning of traditional food pesan tlengis in Werdi Bhuwana Village, Mengwi District, Badung Regency. The research method with a descriptive qualitative approach uses several purposefully selected informants and data collection techniques are carried out by observation, in-depth interviews, and documentation studies with the theory developed in the form of gastronomic theory along with several microforms, tourism theory, and cultural theory. The results of the research will later show that coconut-based gastronomic forms need to be developed so that they can be used as tourist attractions. Efforts that can be made to develop the gastronomy of traditional food with pesan tlengis are related to the preparation and selection of materials, processing of materials, and presentation of food to be able to create new variants and products of good quality so that tourists can enjoy them. Furthermore, the gastronomic meaning of the pesan tlengis dish has been developed to provide added value to tourists and the people of Werdi Bhuwana Village, Mengwi District, Badung Regency.

KEYWORDS: Gastronomy, Pesan Tlengis, Traditional Food, Tourism, Tourist Attraction

INTRODUCTION

Bali as a destination has a variety of cultures and arts, be it dance, music, painting, sculpture, and food processing, which are often called culinary arts. The island of Bali has a very famous culture such as art, religious rituals, and culinary preparations that can arouse the tastes of tourists who come to Bali. Culinary art or the art of processing food and beverages has been known since ancient times (Sutaguna, 2017b).

For this reason, it is necessary to work hard so that Balinese food has value in the eyes of visiting tourists so that authentic Balinese food will become the basic needs of tourists visiting Bali. According to Arisandi et al., (2019) and Sutaguna et al.,(2020), that Bali still has regional specialties, especially aspects of processing and presentation that need to be developed in modern life to be able to attract tourists who want to enjoy things that are not can be experienced in the daily life of these tourists.

In Bali, in general, food sold in hotels or restaurants mostly sells western (continental) food as the main menu. The reason is that many tourists want to get modern food from abroad or European food. Of course, if something like that happened, it would be very sad. Therefore, efforts are being made to sell authentic Balinese food products, so tourism promotion is needed to improve the local community's economy. This will have a positive impact on tourism in Bali in particular and Indonesia in general through the promotion of culinary tourism and gastronomic potential in an area.

Gastronomic tourism for some circles is misinterpreted with culinary tourism where culinary tourism has a narrow scope. Culinary tourists are only limited to wanting to enjoy well-known foods such as Babi Guling Badung, Gudeg Yogya, SioMay Bandung, and so on. So it does not include activities as described previously as stated by Evirasanti, (2016). Gastronomic tourism which is synergized with other development fields such as agriculture and animal husbandry can be used as an alternative in answering problems related to the synergy between tourism development with agriculture, fisheries, and animal husbandry.

Synergies with agriculture and animal husbandry can be developed with coastal areas that have beautiful beaches with upstream and downstream synergies. In upstream areas such as in mountainous areas or agricultural areas such as northern Badung or northern, western, and eastern Bali, agricultural and livestock products needed in downstream areas can be developed to meet the needs and desires of tourists in downstream areas. The development of agricultural and livestock products in the upstream area which is packaged into an interesting activity can also become a tourist attraction.

One of the developments of agricultural products is food processing such as pesan tlengis whose basic ingredients can be obtained from the local area such as coconut, chilies, base genep spices, and other equipment to process these ingredients into ingredients that are ready to be enjoyed and can also be made as offerings. Materials that are the result of agriculture and animal husbandry of the local community after going through a processing process carried out for generations. Through the observations made, it can be seen that the process of making tlengis food ingredients using simple methods and materials with its uniqueness can be used as a tourist attraction that is synergized with other development fields, namely agriculture. The tangible form of this synergy in the agricultural sector is gastronomic tourism in the form of visiting the initial production site, outdoor recreation, cultural activities, and other interesting activities.

By studying these various theoretical aspects, in particular, what efforts can be made to develop the gastronomy of tlengis message dishes in Werdi Bhuwana Village, and examine what meanings are contained in the transformation of these foods. Based on this, it will be an interesting thing to study and research as an object of academic research. Therefore, this research is expected to produce a study that shows that the direction of destination development, attraction and tourism business in Bali, which must be synergized with other development fields (agriculture, animal husbandry, and fisheries), then the gastronomy of pesan tlengis dishes as a tourist attraction in Bali. Werdi Bhuwana Village, Mengwi District, Badung Regency is quite interesting, and relevant to be researched so that it can become a tourist attraction.

METHODS AND PROCEDURES

This research is located in Werdi Bhuwana Village, Badung Regency. The reason for choosing this location is because Werdi Bhuwana Village is a tourist destination and many restaurants in the area sell traditional Balinese food, especially those made from coconut.

Determination of informants is carried out purposively, namely informants who are selected with certain considerations and goals and are considered potential to provide relevant information with accountable quality until the data obtained is considered saturated. The informants in question are Mr. I Ketut Sadia Wijaya as the Head of Werdi Bhuwana Village, and several other informants. The data collection technique of this research is by using observation, interview, and documentation techniques. The data collection technique used in qualitative research is a recording technique using a camera to take pictures/photos. All data were obtained by recording all activities carried out by tourism actors in Werdi Bhuwana Village, for example in selecting and preparing raw materials, preparing ingredients until they were ready to be cooked, processing ingredients until they were ready to be enjoyed.

This study uses descriptive qualitative analysis techniques, namely analysis based on the data collected, then described in sentences based on the theoretical basis so that clear sentences will be formed and can answer the objectives of this study. The results of the data analysis will be presented formally, namely the presentation of the research results in the form of photo graphs and the informal form in the form of narrative text containing a brief description so that it is easier to understand what happened following what was found and understood in the field.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSIONS

Tourism will be more developed if in an area there is more than one type of tourist attraction. However, several types of tourist attractions need to be considered, so that the development of existing tourist attractions is following the wishes of the potential market to determine the right and appropriate development, it is necessary to make some efforts to develop traditional food, especially gastronomy in processing pesan tlengis in Werdi Bhuwana Village, which can be used as an attraction tourism which includes the preparation of raw materials into food ingredients, food processing, and food presentation which are discussed below.

Material Preparation

In preparing the offerings for processing Pesan Tlengis which are made from coconut oil dregs, the people of Werdi Bhuwana

Village still use traditional and simple methods that are followed from generation to generation so that the quality of the materials used is not guaranteed both in terms of cleanliness and food health. The selection and preparation of the Pesan Tlengis material are as follows in table 3.1:

Table 3.1: Basic Ingredients for the Pesan Tlengis

No	Description	Unit	Volume
1	Coconut oil dregs	grams	500
2	Shallot	grams	85
3	Garlic	grams	50
4	Cayenne pepper	grams	25
5	Galangal	grams	45
6	Turmeric	grams	40
7	Aromatic ginger	grams	15
8	Hazelnut	grams	35
9	Shrimp paste	grams	5
10	Brown sugar	grams	8
11	Salt	grams	5

Source: Werdi Bhuwana Village

From this research, it was tried for 10 servings of Pesan Tlengis, with the ingredients mentioned above directed to choose the best quality ingredients, and cleaned, taking into account hygiene, sanitation, and material safety so that they contain high nutrients, as health needs for those who eat them, or tourists who try to eat it.

Material Processing

In processing food ingredients made from offering materials for processing Pesan Tlengis so that they can be offered as tourist attractions, steps are needed as stated in the Theory of Tourist Attraction and Food Processing Techniques. So that the analysis carried out does not seem too technical, the emphasis in this analysis is on things that have a significant influence on the results obtained. So the foods that can be sought to develop and the things that can be done include:

1. The making of pesan tlengis has its uniqueness so that it can be said that there is uniqueness, originality, authenticity, and diversity that can be used as tourist attractions.
2. The time required for the steaming process should be measured according to the amount of material being boiled because it can affect the final product and the energy required.

So the processing processes related to the use of spices can be described as follows; the use of different spices in each ingredient will make the taste of the food richer and each food will have different and distinctive characteristics in terms of color, taste, and aroma.

Figure 1.The process of creating a pesan tlengis

Source: Werdi Bhuwana Village

Food Serving

Efforts that can be made to develop gastronomy in processing Pesan Tlengis regarding the presentation of coconut -based food as a tourist attraction can be done in the following ways:

1. Pesan Tlengis is a source of protein which in serving Balinese food serves as a side dish (side dish) as a source of protein accompanied by carbohydrates such as rice or ketupat and vegetables as a source of vitamins and minerals. Whereas in continental food presentation, the opposite occurs where the carbohydrate source functions as an accompaniment and a protein source as the main meal. So the pesan tlengis that will be served in serving continental food can serve as a companion food.
2. Due to the unique form of the pesan tlengis and the element of originality, the pesan tlengis can be presented directly without having to make any significant changes.

To realize these efforts, cooperation is needed between travel agents and tour guides who take tourists to Werdi Bhuwana Village with the Village Head and Werdi Bhuwana Village Manager to be able to make tour packages in the form of enjoying rice terraces in Werdi Bhuwana Village. Followed by enjoying lunch (lunch) through buffet service (buffet service) where the menu offered is made from coconut which is used in processing pesan tlengis. Performances of regional arts as entertainment that can be enjoyed by tourists while enjoying lunch (lunch) are also efforts that can be made to add to the lively atmosphere at the banquet which is carried out while still implementing good health protocols.

While the presentation of food to be served in the form of individual portions (individual portion) should follow the rules in serving food as stated by Sutaguna, (2017a). The five senses of humans who first enjoy food are the eyes. So good or bad the appearance of the food served will be enjoyed by the eyes which in turn will affect the appetite of people who enjoy the food.

A dish/food is like a painting and a plate or another tool where it is served in the frame. So in serving food in the form of individual portions, it is necessary to pay attention to things concerning balance (balance between the size of the plate, main dish, sauce and side dish/garnish), Colors (color between the main dish, sauce and side dish/garnish). Preferably more than one so it doesn't look monotonous), Shapes (the shape of food consisting of several kinds is more attractive as well as the color), Texture (even though the texture of the food is not visible and can only be proven by touch, it is also very important to pay attention not to serve it), foods that are all soft textured), Flavor (various aromas of food in one plate will make the food more interesting).

So in presenting food arrangements above the serving place, which involves visual appeal (appearance), efficiency, adaptability (suitability), and simplicity it is also necessary to receive serious attention so that the food looks more attractive. Food or dishes served in individual portions are generally offered on the a la carte menu or table d'hote where the food to be served is prepared and arranged on a plate or other serving place in advance by the cook in the kitchen.

The Meaning of Transforming Traditional Balinese Food Made from Coconut in Werdi Bhuwana Village

1. Economic Meaning

Tourism can develop in an area if tourism activities can have a positive impact on the economy of the local community by Jesslyn et al., (2016). In discussing the economic meaning obtained from gastronomy in the Ulihan tradition, it cannot be separated from the commodification process. The word commodification describes the economic value for something that previously had no value from an economic point of view which is sometimes used to describe market transformations for unique, branded products based on undifferentiated products. Further added by (Dewi et al., (2019), that the commodification of products is the fact that they (the products) were first produced to be exchanged for profit. Commodification has a broad meaning and does not only concern the problem of commodity production of goods and services that are traded. The problem of how these goods and services are distributed and consumed is also included in it.

Economic meaning is obtained by packaging material preparation activities, processing food ingredients into food that is ready to be enjoyed and serving it or packaging it into an interesting story and activity and allowing tourists to participate in the preparation of this material so that it becomes something that can be seen (something to see). done (something to do), and bought (something to buy) which is a requirement of a tourist attraction.

2. Social Meaning

Tourism is an activity that directly touches and involves the community by Adinugraha & H Michael, (2014). Community involvement in tourism activities can be in the form of providing tourism facilities or as workers in fields related to tourism facilities such as tour guides, hotel employees, villas or restaurants, and other types of services. In connection with the economic meaning obtained in the form of an increase in the economy from this community involvement, their social status will automatically increase. This change in social status affects the social order, where all members of the community are needed equally regardless of lineage, caste, and so on.

From the tourist side, the social meaning obtained is in the form of a means to increase social status or degree as well as a means of social interaction to be able to carry out social interaction with colleagues or with the local community being visited. As stated by Sutaguna et al., (2018) tourists choose an area with certain tourist destinations to meet their needs and wants. The biological need for food and drink, especially food and drink that has never been enjoyed in the tourist's home country, can become a prestige that can be shared with colleagues, neighbors, and relatives as a means to improve social status in the tourist's home environment.

So the social meaning obtained from the transformation of traditional Balinese food in Werdi Bhuwana Village from an inter-community perspective can be in the form of interrelationships between community members, social institutions, and the rhythm of community social life.

3. Aesthetic Meaning

As revealed by (Syawalia, 2010) that the dish/food is like a painting and the plate where it is served in the frame. However, this does not mean that it takes as much time to arrange the food on the plate as a painter makes his works, because this can be a bad thing if the food has to be served not fresh (fresh). In presenting food, the following must be considered, namely; Balance (the balance between the size of the plate, main dish, sauce, and side dish/garnish), Colors (the color between the main dish, and accompaniments/garnishes should be more than one so it doesn't look monotonous), Shapes (the shape of food consisting of several kinds is more attractive). as well as the color), Texture (although the texture of the food is not visible and can only be proven by touch, it is also necessary to pay attention not to serve food that is all soft textured), Flavor (various aromas of food in one plate will make the food more interesting).

The development of rural tourism certainly affects the physical, social and cultural environment of the local community. The meaning of aesthetics in the context of environmental conservation is increasing public awareness to maintain their assets in the sense of not being tempted to sell land to investors who want to build tourism facilities in Werdi Bhuwana Village.

CONCLUSION

Based on the previous description, it can be concluded that the efforts that can be made to develop gastronomy on Pesan Tlengis dishes in Werdi Bhuwana Village as a tourist attraction include the selection and preparation of raw materials, preparation of raw materials into ready-to-cook food, processing food ingredients that are ready to be cooked into food that is ready to be served and eaten or enjoyed, and efforts to improve the presentation of the food in question. The meaning of modification of traditional Balinese food in Werdi Bhuwana Village is the economic meaning in the form of added value from commercializing the transformation of traditional Balinese food made from coconut, social meaning in the form of social interaction (social interaction), and job opportunities for the community as well as aesthetic meaning in the form of beauty, beauty, and environmental balance. Werdi Bhuwana village.

SUGGESTIONS

The suggestions that can be submitted in this research are as follows:

1. With the use of local ingredients from coconut in the manufacture of Pesan Tlengis dishes, it is hoped that customers will pay attention to the nutrition of food dishes and the hygiene and sanitation of dishes to customers.
2. By promoting local wisdom in choosing materials, traditional Balinese, to be able to pay attention to the needs and desires of customers for every desired request.

3. Viewed from economic, social, and aesthetic factors, coconut food is very popular in Bali, but internationally, especially for pesan tlengis dishes, it is necessary to make separate methods and presentations so that they can be popularized in promoting local wisdom and attracting tourists to try it.
4. For culinary lovers and tourism actors, pay attention to dishes that are very rare so that they are more promoted and known by tourists, especially dishes made from coconut
5. Especially for Pesan Tlengis and the like, special notes are made and need to be exhibited when there are important events, so that they become more popular.

BIBLIOGRAPHY

1. Adinugraha, A. T., & H Michael, S. (2014). Analysis of the Effect of Food Quality and Price Perception on Consumer Satisfaction D'cost Surabaya. *Hospitality and Service Management*, 3, 643–655.
https://scholar.google.com/scholar?cluster=8515815069512198799&hl=en&as_sdt=0.5
2. Arisandi, K. D., Trianasari, T., & Parma, P. G. (2019). Implementation of Hazard Analysis and Critical Control Point (HACCP) in Food Raw Material Storage at Discovery Kartika Plaza Hotel. *Journal of Hospitality and Tourism Management*, 2(1), 55. <https://doi.org/10.23887/jmpp.v2i1.22089>
3. Dewi, R. P., Ervina, E., & Taufiq, R. (2019). The Role of Food and Beverage Sales Executives in Increasing Revenue at Sheraton Bandung Hotel & Towers. *Tourism*, 5(3), 2800–2811.
4. Evirasanti, M. (2016). Effect of Food Quality, Service Quality and Physical Environment on Satisfaction and Behavioral Intention (Study at Metis Restaurant). *E-Journal of Economics and Business*, Udayana University, 12(5), 4331–4358.
<https://ojs.unud.ac.id/index.php/EEB/article/view/24395/16242>
5. Jesslyn, M., Pricilia, C. W., & Regina, J. (2016). The Influence of Restaurant Atmosphere, Food Quality and Service Quality on Consumers' Perceived Value at De Soematra Restaurant Surabaya. *Journal of Chemical Information and Modeling*, 53(9), 1689–1699. <http://dx.doi.org/10.1016/j.tws.2012.02.007>
6. Sutaguna, I. N. T. (2017a). Adaptation of Basic Indonesian Traditional Food Seasonings. Udayana University.
7. Sutaguna, I. N. T. (2017b). Development of Tape Processing as a Culinary Tourist Attraction in Bongkasa Pertiwi Tourism Village Abiansemal Badung. *Journal of Tourism Analysis*, 17(1), 46–52.
8. Sutaguna, I. N. T., Ariani, N. M., Nyoman, N., Aryanti, S., Eka, A., Putri, T., & Wisata, D. (2018). TOURISM DEVELOPMENT THROUGH TRAINING OF LOCAL CULINARY PRESENTATION TECHNIQUES IN THE WISATA VILLAGE OF PENGWI SUB-DISTRICT OF MEMI, BADUNG REGENCY. *Udayana Serving Bulletin*, 17, 114–119.
9. Sutaguna, I. N. T., Sirna, I. K., & Utama, I. G. B. R. (2020). The Processing Technique of Urutan Celeng as A Superior Product for Culinary Tour in Sangeh Abiansemal Tourism Village, Badung, Bali, Indonesia. *Technium Social Sciences Journal*, 11(1), 292–300. <https://doi.org/10.47577/tssj.v11i1.1460>
10. Sutaguna, I. N. T., Sirna, I. K., & Utama, I. G. B. R. (2020). Transformation of Traditional Food with Duck Basic for Culinary Business Continuity in Ubud Tourist Village, Gianyar, Bali, Indonesia. *Technium: Romanian Journal of Applied Sciences and Technology*, 2(7), 42–49. <https://doi.org/10.47577/technium.v2i7.1638>
11. SYAWALIA, S. (2010). Sanitation Hygiene in the Kitchen (Descriptive Study on Efforts to Maintain Kitchen Sanitary Hygiene at Imari Restaurant, JW MARRIOT Hotel Surabaya). 1–3.
12. <https://drive.google.com/file/d/1aaO3MuIBWNKNovM90qFCGQDj6RFmIX-G/view>

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